

A New Complex of Cobalt with Nioxime and Iodine

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This paper deals with the preparation of a new complex of cobalt with nioxime in the presence of iodine. The complex was completely extracted from acidic medium (pH = 1-3) by a mixture of chloroform and iso-amyl alcohol (3 : 1 V/V). The presence of large quantities of Ni and Fe did not affect the method of extraction.

This complex of cobalt exhibits maximum absorption at 290 nm, 370 nm and 460 nm while Ni and Fe ions did not show maximum absorption at 460 nm.

The quantitative determination of traces of elements is considered of interest in modern inorganic analysis. In many industrial processes it is found necessary to determine quantitatively the presence of cobalt and nickel. The reagent used for the determination of either of these elements would interfere with the other. Therefore it was thought necessary to find a specific reagent for their determination or a method to reduce the influence of one element on the other.

A number of organic reagents are used for this purpose, i.e., α -nitroso- β -naphthol, nitroso-R-salt and oximes (e.g., α -furalmonoxime, α -furaldioxime, dimethylglyoxime and 1,2-cyclohexanedionedioxime called "nioxime"¹⁻⁴.

Cobalt (II) can be extracted to a small extent by a solution of chloroform in nioxime and extensively by an iso-amyl alcohol solution of nioxime².

Burger⁵ has studied the complex formed by cobalt with dimethylglyoxime in presence of iodine and has suggested the formation of $\text{Co}(\text{DH}_2)(\text{DH})\text{I}'_2$ (where DH_2 refers to undissociated form of dimethylglyoxime and DH refers to dissociated form.). This complex has two absorption peaks at 330 and 435 nm while ions of Zn, Cu, Ni and Fe do form complexes with dimethylglyoxime in the presence of iodine but do not have maximum absorption at 435 nm. In the present work the use of nioxime and iodine has proved to be superior in the selective determination of cobalt.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nioxime (m.p. 189°) obtained from Aldrich Chemical Co., Inc., was used without further purification. All other substances used in this work were of AnalaR quality. Stock aqueous solution of cobalt(II) was assayed using α -nitroso- β -naphthol⁶.

Equal volumes (usually 10 ml) of aqueous and organic solutions of known composition were equilibrated by rapid shaking in glass separatory funnels for at least one hour at room temperature ($24^\circ \pm 3^\circ$). Experiments showed that complete equilibrium occurred within 1 min. Subsequently, the phases were separated and samples were taken for spectrophotometric or radiometric analysis.

Spectrophotometric measurements were made using Beckman DU spectrophotometer. Radiometric assay of cobalt was done using well-type scintillation detector. The pH of aqueous phase was determined after equilibration using a PYE type pH meter.

The initial concentration of the solutions used were :

- (a) 0.1M of oximes in water;
- (b) 0.1M of $CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $NiSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ and $FeSO_4$ in water;
- (c) 0.1M iodine dissolved in 0.2M iodide solution;
- (d) $4.4 \times 10^{-5} M$ of Co^{60} as perchlorate in 0.1M $HClO_4$ and 0.1M $NaClO_4$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The extraction of cobalt with oximes as a function of the pH of the aqueous phase : The distribution of cobalt ($3.46 \times 10^{-5} M$) from an aqueous solution of the oximes having a known

Fig. 1. The extraction of cobalt with oximes as a function of the pH of the aqueous phase.

- I (Δ) Chloroform and α -furilmonoxime.
- II (\odot) " " α -furildioxime.
- III (\bullet) " " Dimethylglyoxime.
- IV (\square) Chloroform - Iso-amyl alcohol and nioxime in presence of iodine and iodide.

pH into chloroform was investigated radiometrically as a function of pH , ranging between 1 and 13, and the distribution of cobalt from an aqueous solution of nioxime in the presence of iodine and iodide into a 1 : 3 mixture of iso-amyl alcohol and chloroform as a function of pH of the aqueous phase. The results are shown in Fig. 1.

The latter oxime is found to be the best for the complete extraction of cobalt from acidic medium ($pH \sim 1$). The use of mixtures of iso-amylalcohol and chloroform in 1 : 3 proportions was also shown to give complete extraction.

The absorption spectra of the cobalt-oxime complexes in organic solutions : The absorption spectra of the cobalt-oxime complexes extracted into organic phase was measured by adjusting the conditions of both phases such as to give maximum extraction as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The extraction of cobalt(II) from an aqueous phase by different oximes. Absorption spectra of organic phase.

- I (□) Chloroform and Dimethylglyoxime.
 II (●) „ „ α -Furildioxime.
 III (○) „ „ α -Furilmonoxime.

IV (◇) Chloroform - Iso-amyl alcohol and nioxime in presence of iodide and iodine.

It can be seen that only α -furilmonoxime and nioxime (in presence of iodine and iodide) complexes absorb in the visible region.

The absorption spectra of the organic phase in the extraction of cobalt from an aqueous phase in absence and presence of iodine and iodide are shown in Fig. 3. The absorption

Fig. 3. Absorption spectra :

- I (□) Chloroform-Iso-amyl alcohol and nioxime alone (without cobalt);
- II (●) Chloroform-Iso-amyl alcohol and nioxime in presence of iodine and iodide (without cobalt);
- III (△) Chloroform-Iso-amyl alcohol and cobalt nioxime complex in presence of iodide only;
- IV (⊙) Chloroform-Iso-amyl alcohol and cobalt nioxime complex in presence of iodine only;
- V (⬡) Chloroform-Iso-amyl alcohol and cobalt nioxime complex in presence of iodine and iodide.

at 460 nm is clearly greater for the nioxime-iodine and iodide system. The use of this system for the determination of cobalt has several advantages among which are :

- (a) nickel and iron do form complexes with nioxime in the presence of iodine but do not have maximum absorption at 460 nm; and
- (b) Ni and Fe do not interfere with the determination of cobalt.

Consequently, 1,2-cyclohexanedionedioxime with iodine and iodide appears to be a good reagent for the determination of cobalt alone and in presence of large quantities of nickel and iron as will be confirmed by further research.

R E F E R E N C E S

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